

Kinetics and Mechanism of Iodine Oxidation of Coordinated Formate

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The kinetics and mechanism of iodine oxidation of coordinated formate in formatopentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate have been investigated. The order of the reaction both with respect to the oxidant and the substrate is unity. The reaction is catalysed by iodide ion. I_3^- seems to be the active oxidising species. Effects of pH and ionic strength on the rate of the reaction have been examined. The rate and activation parameters have been evaluated and a possible mechanism suggested.

It has been established that HOI is the active oxidising species for sugars¹ and hydrazine² in the iodine oxidation of these substrates. However, in case of iodine oxidation of formate³, I_2 has been shown to be the active oxidising species. These findings indicate that for iodine oxidation the nature of the active oxidising species is different for different substrates. Literature indicates that iodine oxidation of substrates coordinated to a suitable metal-ion centre has not been studied as yet. The kinetics of chlorine⁴ and bromine⁵ oxidation of coordinated formate has been reported from this laboratory. The present communication reports the kinetics of iodine oxidation of coordinated formate in formatopentaamminecobalt(III) ion. An attempt has been made to understand the mechanism of oxidation and to establish the nature of the active oxidising species.

Experimental

Formatopentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate, $[(NH_3)_5CoOCO(H)(ClO_4)_2]$, has been prepared by published method⁶. The purity of the complex is checked by estimating cobalt and formate as described earlier⁶. Solutions of sodium perchlorate and sodium iodide, standardised by ion exchange method⁶, have been used to adjust ionic strength and $[I^-]$, respectively. pH of the reaction solution has been maintained by using sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer. Deionised water distilled from alkaline potassium permanganate solution has been used throughout the experiment. A stoichiometry of one mole of oxidant to one mole of the substrate is found by carrying out the reaction with excess of iodine and estimating the unreacted iodine after the completion of the reaction. The course of the reaction is followed by titrating the unreacted iodine with standard sodium thiosulphate solution using starch solution as indicator. The reaction has been carried out in flasks painted black to avoid the action of light, if any.

Results and Discussion

The reaction between iodine and formatopentaamminecobalt(III) ion has been studied under second order conditions. The observed second order rate constant, k_{obs} , has been calculated by the method of least square. The k_{obs} values and the corresponding least square deviation are recorded in Tables 2 and 3. The rate constant (k_{obs}) is found not to vary with change in either the oxidant or the substrate concentrations. The rate constant is found to increase with decreasing ionic strength (Table 1) and increasing $[I^-]$ (Table 2). It is found to be unchanged with the variation of pH (Table 3) of the reaction medium.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON OBSERVED SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT

Complex] = $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Iodine] = $4.4 \times 10^{-3} M$, pH = 5.6, $[I^-] = 0.14 M$, Temp. = $70.2 \pm 0.1^\circ$

	Ionic strength (M)				
	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6
$10^3 k_{obs} (M^{-1} sec^{-1})$	4.49	4.22	4.20	3.32	2.78
	(±0.18)	(±0.25)	(±0.27)	(±0.31)	(±0.33)

Iodine in aqueous media, in presence of iodide, is known to exist in the form of various species^{7,8} as per the following equilibria :

It is reported that K_1 is of the order⁹ of 10^8 at 38° and K_2 is of the order¹⁰ of 10^{-13} at 25° . Since the reaction has been studied in acidic pH range (4.0 to 5.6) and the value of K_2 is quite small, it is obvious that the concentration of HOI is very small and hence this species may not act as the oxidant species. Present kinetic results (see below) indicate that HOI is not the oxidising species for the present

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING IODINE CONCENTRATION ON OBSERVED SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT
[Complex] = $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Iodine] = $4.4 \times 10^{-3} M$, Ionic strength = $0.3 M$, pH = 5.6

	Temp. = $70.2 \pm 0.1^\circ$					
$10^3 k_{obs} (M^{-1} sec^{-1})$	$[I^-] (M)$	0.07	0.14	0.186	0.256	0.30
		2.88 ± 0.54	4.22 ± 0.25	7.51 ± 0.15	9.30 ± 1.20	13.67 ± 0.26
	Temp. = $75.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$					
$10^3 k_{obs} (M^{-1} sec^{-1})$	$[I^-] (M)$	0.064	0.125	0.166	0.228	0.269
		8.15 ± 0.58	10.05 ± 1.30	14.20 ± 3.3	18.10 ± 3.0	22.75 ± 2.40
	Temp. = $80.5 \pm 0.1^\circ$					
$10^3 k_{obs} (M^{-1} sec^{-1})$	$[I^-] (M)$	0.05	0.14	0.186	0.256	0.30
		7.01 ± 0.32	22.1 ± 2.1	30.85 ± 1.20	35.10 ± 2.50	38.92 ± 3.62

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING pH ON OBSERVED SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT
[Complex] = $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Iodine] = $4.4 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[I^-] = 0.07 M$, Ionic strength = $0.30 M$, Temp. = $70.2 \pm 0.1^\circ$

	pH				
	4.0	4.4	4.8	5.2	5.6
$10^3 k_{obs} (M^{-1} sec^{-1})$	2.85 ± 0.43	2.73 ± 0.33	2.81 ± 0.25	2.88 ± 0.45	2.87 ± 0.27

TABLE 4—RATE AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

	Temp. ($^\circ C$)			$\Delta H^\ddagger (K \text{ cal/mole})$	$\Delta S^\ddagger (\text{e.u.})$
	70.2 ± 0.1	75 ± 0.1	80.5 ± 0.1		
$10^3 k (M^{-1} sec^{-1})$	4.52	7.18	12.64	23.9	4.6

system. If this species would have been the oxidising species, the rate should have increased with increasing pH (eq. 2). This has not been observed in the pH range studied. Higher pH was not maintained to avoid base hydrolysis of the substrate (here the metal complex).

If $[I_2]_T$ and $[I_2]_f$ be the total and free iodine concentrations, respectively, then using eq. 1, it is possible to make the following deductions:

$$[I_2]_f = \frac{[I_2]_T}{1 + K_1 [I^-]} \quad \dots (3)$$

and $[I_3^-] = \frac{K_1 [I_2]_T [I^-]}{1 + K_1 [I^-]} \quad \dots (4)$

Hayakawa and Nakamura⁹ have reported that the values of K_1 are 1010 and 550 at 9.5 and 38°, respectively. In view of the high value of K_1 it is reasonable to apply the following approximation (eq. 5):

$$1 + K_1 [I^-] \approx K_1 [I^-] \quad \dots (5)$$

Using eq. 5, it is possible to deduce eqs. 6 and 7 from eqs. 3 and 4, respectively.

$$[I_2]_f = \frac{[I_2]_T}{K_1 [I^-]} \quad \dots (6)$$

$$[I_3^-] = [I_2]_T \quad \dots (7)$$

If iodine molecule is assumed to be the oxidising species, eq. 6 indicates that the rate constant should increase with decreasing iodide concentration which

is contrary to observation. The rate constant increases with the increase of iodide concentration (Table 3). Plots of k_{obs} versus $[I^-]$ yield perfectly straight lines passing through the origin. The assumption that I_3^- directly oxidises the substrate in the rate determining step and that the increase in rate with increase in $[I^-]$ is due to an increase in $[I_3^-]$ is untenable because eq. 7 indicates that almost all the iodine molecules are present in the form of I_3^- ions. The catalysis of the reaction by iodide can be explained by assuming the following mechanism:

(A)

Scheme 1

The mechanism presented in Scheme 1 indicates the formation of a seven coordinated reaction intermediate of the type A followed by its reaction with I_3^- in rate step to form the products. Though seven-coordinated cobalt(III) species are of rare occurrence, the formation of such species in some reactions has been indicated^{11,12}. If a seven coordinated intermediate of the type A is formed, this species is expected to be thermodynamically less stable (low value of K). However, our results reveal that this

species is kinetically significant. The rate law for the mechanism presented in Scheme 1 is given by eq. 9.

$$\text{Rate} = k'K [\text{complex}]_T [I^-] [I_3^-] \quad \dots (9)$$

Using eq. 7 one obtains eq. 10 from eq. 9

$$\text{Rate} = k'K [\text{complex}]_T [I^-] [I_3^-] \quad \dots (10)$$

In eq. 9, $[\text{complex}]_T$ indicates total concentration of the formate complex. The observed second order rate constant, k_{obs} , is obviously given by eq. 11 which explains the observed linear plot of k_{obs} versus $[I^-]$.

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k[I^-] \quad \dots (11)$$

(where $k'K = k$)

The k values have been calculated from eq. 11 by the method of least square. The k values along with the activation parameters calculated from Eyring equation have been given in Table 4.

The species A presented in Scheme 1 may be visualised to be one in which neither the Co-I bond is sufficiently formed nor the cobalt-formate bond is sufficiently extended, for if the latter is sufficiently extended it would behave almost as a free ligand system and the rates of reaction of free and coordinated formates with iodine would be comparable which has not been observed. The rate constant for the oxidation of free formate by iodine has been reported⁹ to be $(11 \pm 1) \times 10^{-2} M^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$ at 35° while that of formate complex is $4.52 \times 10^{-2} M^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$ at 70° (Table 3, this work).

These data indicate that the reactivities of free and coordinated formates with iodine are not the same. The reasons for the change in reactivity between the free and the coordinated formates are considered below. The mechanism presented in Scheme 1 indicates that I_3^- does not oxidise the parent complex ion $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoOCHO}^{2+}$, rather it prefers to oxidise the species of type A. In this context the following points may be considered. Saffir and Taube¹³ have observed that the rate of oxidation of coordinated oxalate in $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoOC}_2\text{O}_4^+$ by Ce(IV) is much smaller than that of free oxalate and Ce(IV). They have explained that the low reactivity in case of coordinated ligand is due to the fact that electron transfer from a ligand coordinated to a metal ion centre becomes difficult due to the pull exerted by the metal centre on the escaping electron. Gould and Srinivasan¹⁴ have recently observed that mandelate, lactate and benzilate are oxidised by Ce(IV) at about a rate 100 to 1000 times faster than their $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co(III)}$ derivatives. They have also explained this difference in reactivity in a manner similar to Taube. It therefore emerges from the findings of Taube¹³ and Gould¹⁴ that when an oxidisable substrate is coordinated to a metal ion centre it becomes more difficult for the electron to

escape from the substrate to the oxidant. This appears to be the reason for which the formate complex, $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoOCHO}^{2+}$ does not react with I_3^- . However, formation of the species of the type A reduces the positive charge on the metal by one unit and the lower charge in turn exerts a lower pull on the outgoing electron which makes a favourable situation for the transfer of the electron from the ligand to the oxidant.

The foregoing discussions indicate that the reaction occurs between the species A and I_3^- . Since the reactants (A and I_3^-) are oppositely charged it is expected that the rate constant should increase with decreasing ionic strength which has indeed been the case (Table 1).

When carboxylatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes containing two-electron reducing carboxylates are oxidised, the products are either $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})^{3+}$ or Co^{2+} or both depending on the nature of the oxidant used and life time of the reaction intermediate generated¹³⁻¹⁵. In the present investigation $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})^{3+}$ is shown to be the only reaction product⁶ as has been indicated in Scheme 1. Further, the fact that Co^{2+} is not formed as the reaction product reveals that under the temperature range studied, the formate complex (a Co^{3+} system) is not reduced by I^- ion present in the reaction medium.

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